

HOMOGENISATION CAN HELP THE DESIGN OF NEW SYNTACTIC FOAMS.

Abdelwahed Ben Hamida
Université de Paris VI

Laboratoire Mécanique, Modélisation et Calcul.
BP 161 F-75252 PARIS Cedex 05.

Yann-Hervé De Roeck
Ifremer

Service Structures et Ouvrages en Mer.
BP 70 F-29280 BREST.

March 26, 1993

Abstract

Syntactic foams consist of hollow glass microspheres cast in a thermosetting resin. In this study, we have improved a micromechanical approach for modelling this composite material, namely a software tool based upon the homogenisation of the periodic media. Indeed, two complementary physical parameters are now taken into account: the actual binomial distribution of the diameters of the spheres, both for size and composition ratios; and the mechanical effects of water absorption, for which hygroelastic homogenised moduli are now available.

1 Introduction

Syntactic foams consist of hollow glass microspheres cast in a thermosetting resin. In submarine applications, the high strength to weight ratio of this composite material favours its usage both for buoyancy and also for structural parts such as sandwich panels. By a micromechanical approach, several methods are used to predict the behaviour of the foam from the knowledge of the properties of the components. Such tools must be improved, especially in order to help designing new products that could stand high pressures as deep as 6000 meters undersea.

Among these methods, the homogenisation of periodic media assumes a periodicity of the material at a very small scale. Although - in spite of its etymology - the actual arrangement of the hollow spheres in a syntactic - *ordered* - foam does not coincide with a crystalline network, this method has been successfully developed, with the following main advantage: once a microscopic basic cell is defined (one space period of the model), a detailed finite element computation is performed. This leads not only to averaged values of the stress-deformation behaviour, but also to the knowledge of microscopic stresses, from which failure criteria of the components can be evaluated. It is thus easy to construct a complete macroscopic elastic domain for the composite material.

The aim of this study is to fulfil some requirements of the material designers, by taking into account two physical parameters that were previously ignored:

- the actual distribution of the diameters of the spheres can not be described by an averaged value, because for maximising the void, two species of hollow spheres, with average diameters

in a ratio varying from 2.5 to 10 depending on the manufacturer, are mixed together. Several crystalline cubic networks, that can provide the high compactness, and two different species are investigated here.

- when water absorption cannot be avoided, namely when the foam is used outside the structure, not only the buoyancy is altered, but also the stiffness of the material. This might come from the lower compression strength of the moistened resin and from the differential swelling of the resin as compared with the glass, that generates internal stresses at the microscopic level. The original numerical model has been modified to simulate this phenomenon by a hygroscopic expansion of the resin in the elementary cell, which affects the homogenised moduli. No attempt is made so far to couple the water diffusion and the elastic alteration.

2 Homogenisation of periodic media, with stationary hygroelasticity.

The theory of the homogenisation of periodic media relies on the two following fundamental assumptions:

- the arrangement of the composite is periodic,
- the period is small with respect to the dimensions of the structure.

In the case of syntactic foams, the diameter of the glass inclusions varies between 5 and 200 micrometers: thus, the microscopic and the macroscopic scales differ enough to justify the homogenisation (typically, the size of a basic cell containing the full periodic pattern tends to zero).

However, the foam does not show any periodicity, due to the processes used for manufacturing it: either the hollow spheres are mixed with the resin before moulding, or the resin is injected under vacuum into the mould which has been previously filled with the spheres and shaken, in order to maximise the density of inclusions. But, by systematically checking if the results of the numerical model are isotropic, periodicity appears not to be a very misleading hypothesis.

We now briefly recall the computational technique. The so-called “imposed macroscopic deformations” homogenisation method of periodic media [1] is being used, as it fits well the usual finite element codes: indeed, a displacement method is also involved for solving the structural analysis problem at the microscopic scale.

Scaling between both media, microscopic and macroscopic, is achieved by averaging some quantities over the volume of the periodic pattern, also named the basic cell and quoted \mathbf{Y} : ($\|\mathbf{Y}\|$, volume of the basic cell)

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma &= \langle \sigma \rangle = \frac{1}{\|\mathbf{Y}\|} \int_{\mathbf{Y}} \sigma dy && \text{macro- and microstresses,} \\ \mathbf{E} &= \langle e(u) \rangle = \frac{1}{\|\mathbf{Y}\|} \int_{\mathbf{Y}} e(u) dy && \text{macro- and microstrains.} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

In fact, all mathematical proofs are made by tending to the limit by an asymptotic development over the diameter of the cell \mathbf{Y} . The case of linear hygroelastic materials under small strains is managed by analogy with thermoelasticity [2], because of the similarity of the governing constitutive equations.

Naming a the tensor of the local stiffnesses, α the tensor of the hygroelastic expansion, we first assume that the moisture content m is uniform in the basic cell, and therefore equal to

the stationary macroscopic moisture content. The homogenised stiffnesses \mathbf{Q} and expansion \mathbf{A} are extracted from the coefficients of the following equation, which relates the macroscopic stresses Σ to the macroscopic strains \mathbf{E} :

$$\Sigma = \mathbf{Q} \cdot (\mathbf{E} - \mathbf{A}m) \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{with } e(u) \text{ } \mathbf{Y}\text{-periodic,} && \sigma \cdot \vec{n} \text{ } \mathbf{Y}\text{-antiperiodic,} \\ &\text{solutions of } \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \operatorname{div} \sigma = 0 & \text{in } \mathbf{Y} \\ \sigma = a \cdot (e(u) - \alpha m) & \text{in } \mathbf{Y} \\ \langle e(u) \rangle = \mathbf{E} \end{array} \right. && (3) \end{aligned}$$

Due to the linearity of the problem - Equations 2 and 3 -, the elastic and hygroscopic contributions can be separated, and the solution (u, σ) is searched for on the following basis:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} u = E_{hk} v^{hk} + m \psi \\ \sigma = E_{hk} s^{hk} + m c \end{array} \right.$$

where (v^{hk}, s^{hk}) and (ψ, c) are the solutions of the seven independent problems:

$$\begin{aligned} &e(v^{hk}) \text{ } \mathbf{Y}\text{-periodic,} && s^{hk} \cdot \vec{n} \text{ } \mathbf{Y}\text{-antiperiodic,} \\ &\text{solutions of } \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \operatorname{div} s^{hk} = 0 & \text{in } \mathbf{Y} \\ s^{hk} = a \cdot e(v^{hk}) & \text{in } \mathbf{Y} \\ \langle e(v^{hk}) \rangle = \Pi^{hk} & \text{with } \Pi_{ij}^{kh} = \frac{1}{2}(\delta_{ik} \cdot \delta_{jh} + \delta_{ih} \cdot \delta_{jk}), \end{array} \right. && (4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{and } \psi \text{ } \mathbf{Y}\text{-periodic,} && c \cdot \vec{n} \text{ } \mathbf{Y}\text{-antiperiodic,} \\ &\text{solutions of } \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \operatorname{div} c = 0 & \text{in } \mathbf{Y} \\ c = a \cdot (e(\psi) - \alpha) & \text{in } \mathbf{Y}. \end{array} \right. && (5) \end{aligned}$$

In order to solve Problems 4 in a space of kinematic fields with periodic displacements (instead of periodic deformations), a change of variables is used:

$$\chi = \langle \nabla u \rangle y - u \quad (6)$$

$$\tau = a \cdot e(\chi) = a \cdot E - \sigma \quad (7)$$

from which Problems 4 become:

$$\begin{aligned} &\chi^{hk} \text{ } \mathbf{Y}\text{-periodic,} && \tau^{hk} \cdot \vec{n} \text{ } \mathbf{Y}\text{-antiperiodic,} \\ &\text{solutions of } \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \operatorname{div} \tau^{hk} = \operatorname{div} (a \cdot \Pi^{hk}) & \text{in } \mathbf{Y} \\ \tau^{hk} = a \cdot e(\chi^{hk}) & \text{in } \mathbf{Y} \end{array} \right. && (8) \end{aligned}$$

In the case of the syntactic foam, we are not allowed to assume that the displacement field u might be extrapolated to 0 in the empty part of the domain (interior of the hollow spheres). The definition of the averaged quantities in Equations 1 and 6 must be replaced by integrals on the boundary of the solid domain $\partial \mathbf{Y}_{\mathbf{P}}$: (\otimes tensor product)

$$\langle \nabla u \rangle = \frac{1}{\|\mathbf{Y}\|} \int_{\partial \mathbf{Y}_{\mathbf{P}}} \vec{u} \otimes \vec{n} d\Gamma \text{ and } \langle E \rangle = \frac{(\langle \nabla u \rangle + \langle \nabla u \rangle^T)}{2}.$$

The computation of the displacement fields χ^{hk} and ψ is undertaken by the finite element method, namely using the MODULEF library code [3], with regular elastic elements for Problems 8 and thermoelastic elements for Problem 5. The homogenised coefficients are obtained by combining Equations 2, 5, 6, 7 and 8:

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{ijhk} &= \langle a_{ijhk} \rangle - \langle a_{ijpq} \cdot e_{pq}(\chi^{hk}) \rangle, \\ A_{ij} &= \mathbf{Q}^{-1} (\langle a_{ijpq} \cdot \alpha_{pq} \rangle - \langle a_{ijpq} \cdot e_{pq}(\psi) \rangle). \end{aligned}$$

Thanks to these coefficients, a finite element structural analysis can be performed that leads to the macroscopic fields of stresses or strains. Then, the linear problem of determining the microscopic fields is solved by a linear combination of the results of the elementary load cases χ^{hk} and ψ . The damage criteria of the materials can thus be checked locally. This process allows us to build the elastic domain for the composite material and it helps to determine whether the damage comes from the resin (plastification, microcracking) or from the hollow spheres (implosion).

3 Basic cell with two species of hollow spheres

Studies to optimise the buoyancy of syntactic foams have shown [4] that the compactness of inclusions could increase if two species with different diameters were used. This developed into an industrial process, and foams with two kind of hollow spheres can be found: the ratio of the diameters may vary from 2.5 to 10.

Several types of basic cells have been studied to model syntactic foams by the homogenisation of periodic media, all based upon crystalline networks. Table 1 sums up the easy computation of the compactness for three networks: regular cubic, body centered and face centered cubic. For each network, the maximum compactness is given with one and two species, and in the latest case, the ratio of the two diameters and the relative proportion of the species. In the case of the regular cubic network, only one kind of spheres can be introduced.

Up to now, our computations were only able to model a network with one kind of diameter, although the choice between the regular and the centered cubic networks was already open. In order to improve the simulation of the arrangement of the actual foams, we have thus introduced into our code the bigrularity of the hollow spheres and a new type of network, the face centered cubic. Indeed, the last model of Table 1 coincides very well with the data of an optimised formulation that has been proposed in [4]:

- the compactness of the foam (relative volume of the inclusions): $\tau = 0.63$;
- the diameters of the spheres are dealt with by two peaks which are centered around 35 and 86 μm , corresponding to a ratio $\frac{D_1}{D_2} = 2,46$;
- the proportion of large versus small microspheres is very close: $n_1/n_2 = 30\% / 70\%$.

The computations described in §2 are simplified by taking into account the planes of symmetry of a cubic basic cell [5]. The computational domain is limited to an eighth of the basic cell, as shown in Figure 1 and only three load cases are to be considered: the right-hand sides χ_{11}, χ_{12} and χ_{22} are computed at once, but for obtaining the homogenised coefficients, only problems related to χ_{11} and χ_{12} have to be solved. Such remarks lead to an efficient software whereas the proposed models (the geometry of the crystalline network for instance) tend to be more and more complex.

New meshes have been also drawn in order to avoid any worsening of the finite elements when the compactness increases (close to τ_m). Indeed, the volume around the inclusions contains many

Crystalline network		1 species compactness (τ_m).	2 species compactness (τ_m), diameters ratio ($\frac{D_1}{D_2}$), proportion (n_1/n_2).
Cubic		$\tau_m = \frac{\pi}{6}$ = 0,52	not possible
Body Centered Cubic		$\tau_m = \frac{\pi\sqrt{3}}{8}$ = 0,68	$\tau_m = \frac{\pi}{6} [(\sqrt{3}-1)^3 + 1]$ = 0,73 $\frac{D_1}{D_2} = \frac{1}{(\sqrt{3}-1)}$ = 1,37 $n_1/n_2 = 50 \% / 50 \%$
Face Centered Cubic		$\tau_m = \frac{\pi}{3\sqrt{2}}$ = 0,74	$\tau_m = \frac{\pi}{6} [1 + 3(\sqrt{2}-1)^3]$ = 0,64 $\frac{D_1}{D_2} = \frac{1}{(\sqrt{2}-1)}$ = 2,41 $n_1/n_2 = 25 \% / 75 \%$

Table 1: Comparison of the maximal compactities for different networks.

concave parts that are difficult to mesh. To overcome this fact, we have introduced a spherical layer of resin that fictitiously surrounds each hollow sphere. The boundaries of these newly defined spheres (glass+resin layer) are tangential, as in the case of the optimal compactness when the glass spheres are in contact. Therefore, it is possible to narrow the distance between spheres (and let it tend towards 0) without deteriorating the rest of the mesh.

The software has been tested with a syntactic foam with the following properties:

- Composition of the mixture:
 - proportion of resin: 40 % (1- τ)
 - 2 species: 30 % of 86 μm , 70 % of 35 μm
 - averaged ratio of the thickness over the diameter of the wall of the spheres:
 $\frac{e}{D} = 0,0223$
- Properties of the components:

	Young modulus	Poisson coefficient	relative density
Resin	E = 3 513 MPa	$\nu = 0.35$	d = 1,2
Glass	E = 62 000 MPa	$\nu = 0.22$	d = 2,55

Table 2 presents for each model the homogenised coefficients E, ν and G, compared to those observed in mechanical tests on the foam and to those estimated by the analytical, so-called “three-phases media” method, that we have implemented [6]. The numbers of elements and of degrees of freedom of the finite element discretisation are also noted in order to show that all these models have the same order of refinement.

The homogenisation method of periodic media leads to an equivalent quasi-isotropic material. This means that E, ν and G, when extracted from the stiffness matrix computed on the main axes of the cell, must be independent coefficients. As they do not verify the relationship: $E = 2 G (1 + \nu)$, it appears that the Young modulus varies with the direction of the tensile test. In [7], it is shown that the extreme values of E are reached in the directions of the

Figure 1: $1/8^{\text{th}}$ of the cell for a body centered and a centered faces cubic respectively. Elements are P1-tetraedra.

axes and of the diagonals of the cell. Moreover, the following coefficient appears to be a good means of checking the deviation from isotropy of the model (results are also given in Table 2):

$$\Theta = \frac{\frac{1}{E_{\max}} - \frac{1}{E_{\min}}}{\frac{1}{E}} = \frac{2}{3} \frac{1 + \nu}{G} \left| G - \frac{E}{2(1 + \nu)} \right|$$

references	E (Mpa)	ν				
Tests	3 450	0,29				
3 Phases	3 299	0,31				
models	E (Mpa)	ν	G (Mpa)	Θ %	nb elt	nb dof
bcc 1 species	3 372	0,30	1 298	0,50	9072	5697
bcc 2 species	3 391	0,30	1 302	0,20	7776	4992
fcc 2 species	3 419	0,30	1 305	0,35	9072	5949

Table 2: Elastic moduli from homogenisation for the following models: body centered (bcc) and face centered cubic (fcc) with 1 or 2 species.

From Table 2, our homogenisation models of periodic media obviously yield closer results to the tests than the analytical model of the 3 phases method. The regular cubic network has not been tested, because its maximum compactness is limited to 0.52, far below the actual 0.63 of the reference foam.

Firstly, a better quality result is achieved for a body centered network if two species are used instead of only one, both for the Young's modulus and for the distance to isotropy. In this case where the proportion of small and large spheres must be equal, see Table 1, the actual ratio of the diameters cannot be reproduced either. Thus, the ratio $\frac{D_1}{D_2} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3-1}}$ is used, that corresponds to the maximum compactness: in this way, all small spheres are represented by one in each cell, the compactness is exactly simulated, and the distance between the spheres is maximised (in order to let the resin play its softening role).

The face centered cubic network with one species has not been implemented yet, but it should lead to a relatively strong anisotropy, as does the body centered network with one species. With two species, the face centered cubic network possesses the best approximation of the actual arrangement of the foam and also produces the best estimate of the Young's modulus ($\Delta E/E = 0,9\%$).

4 Simulation of the mechanical effects of the water absorption

At present, syntactic foams are not used for structural parts in submarine applications, but as buoyancy material added outside the vessel, and are thus subjected to the ingress of water. Thus, two properties are mainly studied: the resistance to implosion under very high hydrostatic pressures and the absorption of water that lowers the lift per unit weight.

This last phenomenon should also be taken into account for its mechanical consequences, especially if the foam has a structural role, for instance as the core material of a sandwich panel. Besides the influence of water on the material strengths to failure (already mentioned by [4]: plastification of the resin, oxidation of the glass implying embrittlement), the absorption of water exclusively by the resin can generate microscopic stresses that modify the homogenised behaviours of the composite material.

This partial swelling has been modelled by the hygroelastic Equations 3, in which a uniform moisture content m covers the whole basic cell, and therefore corresponds to the macroscopic moisture content of the foam. Due to the lack of experimental data, the expansion tensor of the resin is computed on the basis of the following assumptions:

- this tensor is isotropic,
- in the foam, no water seeps into the microspheres nor towards the interface glass/resin: therefore, the actual moisture in the resin is increased compared to the macroscopic one,
- no chemical reaction occurs during the swelling process, thus in a stress-free expansion experiment on the resin, the volume of the body grows solely by the added volume of water.

This leads to a definition of α based upon the density of the foam d_{foam} and the compacity τ of the material in the following way:

$$\alpha_{\text{res}} = \frac{d_{\text{foam}}}{3(1 - \tau)}$$

Moreover, the resulting homogenised expansion tensor \mathbf{A} is not diagonal any more, which might be difficult to handle in the macroscopic structural computation. In fact, once again, the deviation from isotropy is small, as is shown in Table 3 when diagonal terms A_{ii} are compared to off-diagonal terms A_{ij} . Here, the face centered cubic network with 2 species shows the best isotropy. The influence of the compacity τ on the homogenised expansion is also to be noted, as it follows the intuitive trend: the more compact foam (in spheres, thus the lighter density), the less hygroscopic expansion to be expected.

It is also understood that this enhancement of the model will be most useful at the microscopic level, for determining local overstresses that affect the failure criteria. Preliminary results show that if the Timoshenko criterion for the buckling of the glass hollow spheres is chosen as the compression failure criterion, the moisture content intervenes linearly.

models	τ	α_{res}	A_{ii}	A_{ij}	τ	α_{res}	A_{ii}	A_{ij}
bcc 1 species	0.60	0.5685	0.3179	0.0177	0.63	0.5913	0.3108	0.0193
bcc 2 species	0.60	0.5685	0.3178	0.0092	0.63	0.5913	0.3108	0.0099
fcc 2 species	0.60	0.5728	0.3237	0.0079	0.63	0.5961	0.3172	0.0095

Table 3: Expansion from homogenisation for the following models: body centered (bcc) and face centered cubic (fcc) with 1 or 2 species.

5 Conclusion

By introducing a second species of spheres and the more sophisticated face centered cubic network, the model by homogenisation of periodic media gives a better representation of real syntactic foams. Both the high compactness of inclusions and the distribution of the diameters of microspheres are now taken into account.

The mechanical effect of the absorption of water by the resin has been modelled by an analogy with thermoelasticity. Indeed, microstresses due to the partial swelling of the resin produce a softening of the material that appears to be qualitatively true. However, further investigations are needed to prove that we remain within the bounds of the numerical model, and that the results coincide with tests.

References

- [1] Bensoussan, A., Lions, J.-L., Papanicolaou, G., *Asymptotic Analysis for Periodic Structures*, North Holland, Amsterdam, 1978.
- [2] Francfort, G., *Homogénéisation et Oscillations Rapides en Thermoélasticité Linéaire*, Comptes-Rendu à l'Académie des Sciences, Paris, t. 295 (4 octobre 1982).
- [3] Bernadou, M., et al, *Modulef : Une Bibliothèque Modulaire d'Éléments Finis*, I.N.R.I.A., Rocquencourt, 1988.
- [4] Fonblanc, G., *Mousses Syntactiques : Matériaux Composites pour Grandes Profondeurs*, Thèse de Doctorat, Université de Bordeaux I, 1986.
- [5] Léné, F., *Contribution à l'Étude des Matériaux Composites et de leur Endommagement*, Thèse d'État, Université de Paris VI, 1984.
- [6] Christensen, R.M., *Mechanics of Composite Materials*, John Wiley and sons. New-York 1979.
- [7] Ben Hamida, A., *Étude Micromécanique des Mousse Syntactiques*, Thèse de Doctorat, Université de Paris VI, 1989.